

EDUCATIONAL PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11146045>

Abstract: this article discusses the problems of the educational system of Uzbekistan and the possibility of solving these problems with the help of modern educational technologies. Opinions on the design of the educational process are also presented.

Key words: education, technology, development, reform, pedagogical approach, design, educational management.

Introduction:

The effectiveness of educational quality seems to be related to the level of professional preparation of students, as well as how the educational process is organized and its quality meets the criteria. This task is the content of a number of legislative and regulatory documents, in particular, the national personnel training program and the socio-economic system of the country.

From the point of view of development, recommendations and principles for specific goals are reflected in its appearance, based on the needs of society, science, culture, technology and modern achievements in the field of technology.

Designing the educational process is a form of pedagogical activity, it is education. The technological structure of the educational process is also a method that guarantees the educational result, and is characterized by the presence of the amount of efficiency. As a result of the analysis of the essence of educational pedagogical practice, several laws of process design were determined. They are as follows:

- the effectiveness of the design of the educational process is provided on the basis of the appropriate coverage of the project with the structural characteristics of the part (technological management, information, social-psychological environment);
- technological means of teaching are selected individually for students according to their characteristics;
- the development of strategies for the individual style of the teacher is selected accordingly;
- feedback on the quality of the design (between the teacher and the student) depends on the design volume, content, as well as the effectiveness of all factors [3. 78-p].

In general educational institutions, the design of the educational process is carried out at two levels:

- at the level of teacher activity (individual activity of the educational process);
- educational management is carried out at the activity level (educational process) [3. 75-p].

In the design of the educational process, not only each component is taken into account, but also the relationship between them is modeled and designed.

The principle of combining students in the technological process is expressed as the main element of the design of the activity model. As part of the educational process, the main systematized content of education and student activity is considered as a technological process, and its content is aimed at mastering the basics of social experience of students. educational activity. The content of education for each subject is determined in accordance with the goals and objectives of general education.

From the point of view of the approach to the organization of the content of active general secondary education, each element should correspond to one of the subject's activities. In turn, the activities of the subject should be represented by a set of understandable models through generalized activity models.

The student activity model is a systematic element that serves to determine the general content of the student's activity. The principle of centralization is built in the following order. It requires increasing: creation of activity models for goals, selection of methods and means of their mastery by students (technological operations), methods of educational activity management (teacher activity) [5. 55-p].

The principle of reflexivity refers to the subject himself, his personal activity and evaluates his knowledge, other people's opinions about him and the relationship between them. It is related to joint activity [5. p. 67]. In the process of design, the teacher is always recommended to take into account the specific and ideal conditions, the needs of students for knowledge, filling their opportunities, personal qualities and abilities, and the possibilities of effective pedagogical activities in the educational process.

The educational project of the educational process created by the principle of reflexivity requires constant correction and completion of the analysis of the needs and capabilities of the participants in the process.

The principle of efficiency describes the simplicity of pedagogical conditions, the achievement of effective results with less time and efforts. Efficiency is the content of models of social experience activity, technological operations, their development, the choice of management methods, the compatibility of teaching activities, teaching tools, the technological process should mean achieving the defined goal with the help of a short time and efforts of the subject.

The principle of multifactoriality. Each educational process represents a number of goals and is carried out under the influence of subjective factors. Among them are socio-economic conditions of life of teachers and students, educational institutions, social-production environment and natural-climatic environment, education, educational and material base of the institution, professional qualifications of teachers. , level in a certain class, educational institution or spiritual-psychological environment, educational opportunities of students, intellectual potential of the class, interpersonal relations in the community. The teacher should take these factors into account when designing the educational process [2. 45-p].

In designing the educational process, the teacher is the creator and executor. Chooses a convenient way to implement the project. Methods of directing students to educational activities, forms of independent education, self-development and self-esteem.

The concept of "pedagogical technology" comes from the fact that two important aspects of pedagogical activity, that is, education and training, should represent the technological

development of the process. The ideal person is to recognize the problem of education as a social necessity, if we consider the process of education and upbringing, to make a decision on a new approach to the organization. Achieving process technology is one of the important pedagogical tasks.

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